

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

The 4th Serbian Conference on Materials Application and Technology - SCOM

October 15th-17th 2025, Belgrade

Wednesday, October 15th, 2025

Vlatacom Institute – Conference hall 09.30-13.00 Registration

Session 1

Session chair Željka Antić

10.00-10.15	Opening ceremony
10.15-10.45	Vlatacom Institute presentation Daniel Mijailović <i>NEXT-EDLC: Carbon-based electrode development for high-performance supercapacitors</i>
10.45-11.30	Tutorial lecture ONLINE Volodymyr Pavlyuk <i>Introduction to Determining Crystal Structure by X-Ray Diffraction</i>
11.30-12.00	Coffee Break
Session 2	
Session chair Vesna Đorđević	
12.00-12.30	Invited lecture Zoran Ristić <i>Data-Driven Thermometry on Mn⁵⁺ Doped Ca₆Ba(PO₄)₄O Phosphor</i>
12.30-12.45	Jan Hočevar <i>Cellulose-Based Hydrogels: Emerging Biomaterials for Sustainable Applications</i>
12.45-13.00	ONLINE Azmat Ullah <i>Optimisation of Titanium Dioxide Photocatalytic Efficiency with Lignin Derived Carbon Quantum Dots</i>
13.00-13.30	Coffee Break
Session 3	
Session chair Ljubica Đačanin Far	
13.30-13.45	Andela Rajčić <i>Photocatalytic and Antimicrobial Properties of Rare-Earth-Doped BiOCl</i>
13.45-14.00	Tamara Ivetić <i>Up-conversion Luminescence and Lifetime Thermometry in Er³⁺/Yb³⁺-doped YNbO₄ Nanophosphors</i>
14.00-14.15	Radu Banica <i>Rapid Synthesis of YBO₃ as Host Materials for Pr³⁺ Doping</i>
14.15-14.30	Cristina Mosoarca <i>Assessment of The Toxicity and Germicidal Activity of Y₂SiO₅:Pr³⁺ and La(PO₃)₃:Pr³⁺ Compounds Against Escherichia Coli</i>
14.30-14.45	George Dima <i>Prediction of 5d Level Absorption Wavelength in Inorganic Hosts: Random Forest Model with SHAP Prioritization Of Candidates</i>
14.45-15.00	Tamara Matić <i>The Ion-Doping of Mesoporous Bioactive Glass Particles</i>
15.00-16.30	Vlatacom Institute exhibition and welcome party

Thursday, October 16th, 2025

Vlatacom Institute – Conference hall 09.30-13.00 Registration

Session 4

Session chair Dušan Božanić

10.00-10.45	Tutorial lecture ONLINE Michal Piasecki <i>How to Effectively Improve the Desired Properties of Energy Harvesting Materials?</i>
10.45-11.00	Danijela Danilović <i>Novel Hybrid Nanomaterials as NIR Light-Driven Nanomotors for Biomedical Applications</i>
11.00-11.15	Anamarija Abu El Rub <i>Solid Lipid-Metal Nanoparticles Functionalized by Amino Acids</i>
11.15-11.45	Coffee Break
Session 5	
Session chair Vesna Lazić	
11.45-12.30	Tutorial lecture ONLINE Oleg Khyzhun <i>Application of X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy for Verification of DFT Band-Structure Calculations of Solids</i>
12.30-12.45	Sofia Maleeva <i>Cr³⁺ Doped Calcium Stannate Persistent Luminescence Material</i>
12.45-13.00	Valentina Nikšić <i>Eco-Safe Bioactive TiO₂ Nanohybrids Functionalized with Green Tea Phenolics</i>
13.00-15.00	Break
Session 6	
Session chair Aleksandar Ćirić	
15.00-15.30	Invited lecture Jelena Papan Djaniš <i>Biomass-Derived Carbon Quantum Dots: Structural Insights and Photoluminescence from Tomato Sources</i>
15.30-15.45	ONLINE Miriama Malček Šimunková <i>Indirect EPR Study of TiO₂ Modified with Natural Extracts</i>
15.45-16.00	ONLINE Michal Malček <i>Hydrogen Binding and Hydrogen Cleavage on Single Metal-Decorated Circumcoronenes</i>

Friday, October 17th, 2025

Vlatacom Institute – Conference hall

Session 7

Session chair Zoran Ristić

10.00-10.45	Tutorial lecture ONLINE Chong-Geng Ma <i>First-Principles Calculations For Intrinsic and Extrinsic Defects In Solids: Methodology and Case Studies</i>
10.45-11.00	Dušan Sredojević <i>Analysis of the Electromagnetic Shielding Properties of Graphene Oxide Coated with Platinum Nanoparticles</i>
11.00-11.15	Milica Maričić <i>Gamma Irradiation Impact on Mechanical, Structural and Optical Properties of Natural Leather</i>
11.15-11.30	Snežana Đurković <i>Physics-Informed Artificial Intelligence Framework for Predicting Luminescence Properties of Cr³⁺-Doped Inorganic Phosphors</i>
11.30	Closing ceremony